

Task Management System

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Abstract

This study introduces a task management system that helps the user by taking the load of organizing tasks according to their priority. The system first authenticates the user using email and password. A user can provide a task name, a task description and a due date and also set a priority (low, medium, or high). The user interface provides the user the ability to edit and delete tasks effortlessly. Users can update their profiles and passwords without any hassle. The application interface provides three tabs, which include a dashboard for an overview of all tasks, a pending section, and a completed section. When a user achieves a target, it automatically goes to the completed section. Both the pending and completed sections have the functionality of filtering tasks by oldest, newest and priority. With a less complicated but functional task management system, users can stay organized without feeling overwhelmed.

Keywords: Task Management, subtask, reminders and notifications, prioritization techniques.

1. Introduction

In our day-to-day lives, we get so busy that we keep forgetting our tasks deadlines. This also creates chaos in the mind, leading to frustration and incomplete tasks piling up. If there is a single task we need to do, then it is easy to complete it on time, but when many tasks are on the table, it becomes difficult to prioritize. There are also other important duties to tackle besides these tasks, and if these tasks are not completed, it becomes really difficult to focus on other activities.

Thus, to address these challenges, the "Task Force : Task Management System" proposed in this paper aims to provide users to tackle tasks. A user requires a system that not only allows them to create and organize tasks but also provides priority-based categorization and an interface that is simple to use.

2. Literature Survey

A significant amount of research has been devoted to web-based task management that allows individuals to manage their tasks. These papers provide a brief introduction to some Task Management Systems, which shed light on how these systems enhance the ability to manage tasks and activities.

In the work [1], the authors propose the necessity and an efficient task organization and management system to provide students with a system that helps them to achieve academic success. The features, which are classification, reminders, and priority settings, are stated to help students manage their social and academic lives more effectively.

In [2], the authors state that a task management system is expected to increase student productivity by providing tools for managing, planning and tracking the task life cycle. The system is designed to help students, who often struggle with time management.

In [3], the authors state that time is a fleeting resource. With the rapid digital transformation and change, users need tools that help them focus on important tasks by setting priorities.

3.Methodology

The methodology section of this research sketches the design and development process undertaken to create the specified system. This system is developed by using the MERN stack.

Frontend (React): React provides a component-based architecture enabling modular and reusable user interface elements that help in the development of task management interfaces.

Backend (Node.js, Express.js) : Node.js enables non-blocking I/O operations, which supports managing multiple users without performance degradation.

Database (MongoDB): MongoDB provides efficient storage for task objects with variable attributes, including priority levels, descriptions and due dates.

3.1 System Architecture

The MERN Stack implements a three-tier architecture including frontend logic, backend logic and data :

Presentation tier (React Frontend): Provides user Interface Components for task creation, filtering and display. Implements responsive design across desktop, tablet, and mobile devices.

Application tier (Express.js /Node.js Backend): Implements logic including user authentication, task management operations ,data validation and access control.

Data tier (MongoDB): Manages user accounts, task data and system configuration.

3.2 Database Schema Design:

Users Collection: Stores user authentication credentials, profile information (name, email, and password), preferences and account status.

Task Collection: Stores individual task documents containing items for task title, description, priority levels, due date, created date and completion Status.

4.Results and Analysis

This project was developed for our college major project.

Figure 1 shows the sign in page of the system. Users can sign in with Email and Password.

Figure 2 shows the dashboard of the user. This page provides an overview of their tasks.

Figure 3 shows the Dashboard of the user.

Figure 4 shows the Pending tasks of the user.

Figure 5 shows the Completed task of the user.

5. Conclusion

Task management System is a web application that aims to provide a functional system to help users accomplish their tasks. Of course, in any system, there may be certain limitations in any project. There is always a potential for further improvements, such as individualized email notifications, reminders and a mobile application for mobile use.

References

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